
INCORPORATING MULTIMEDIA AND TECHNOLOGY TO IMPROVE COMMUNICATION SKILLS AT WTW. INC. JAPAN

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ABSTRACT

The key issues with students' communication skills have been found to be extremely low by online learning during the previous two years according to Covid-19. It negatively affects kids' communication abilities. Direct observation is used to identify issues that are evident from the decline in pupils' English communication skills. Online student exchange is the component of the collaboration project with WTW.Inc. Japan that aims to help students' communication abilities. To carry out the activity, students from around the world share knowledge and create presentations utilizing technology tools like multimedia. The desire and motivation of the students to participate in the activity in this study is indicative of the impact that multimedia has on the presentation. Students in the English Club at SMK TI BALI GLOBAL DENPASAR will be the subject of the study. Observations, teacher and student interviews, and questionnaires are all utilized as qualitative research techniques. The Miles and Huberman methods are used to analyze the data, and a pie chart and narrative data presentation were used to illustrate the questionnaire results. The findings of this study demonstrated the significant positive impact of employing multimedia when giving presentations to students from foreign nations.

Keywords: *Multimedia, Communication skill, WTW program.*

INTRODUCTION

The era of online learning has entered the education system in Indonesia where the learning system without direct face-to-face between teachers and students must be done online by the internet network. All teachers are expected to be able to design learning media as innovations by utilizing the technology. Teachers conduct online learning simultaneously by groups on social media such as WhatsApp, telegram, Instagram, zoom applications or other learning media. In

this way, teachers can ensure that students take part in learning at the same time, even at different places. Another challenge lies in the level of comfort and enjoyment of students in the online learning process. The problem that arises is the interaction of students who are weak and influenced by the level of boredom of students who do not have the motivation to learn anymore. Effective communication skills are the basis for success in many aspects of life. A modern education concept with many

advantages in preparing students to become the best professionals in a given platform. Students with effective communication skills be more likely to contribute to class discussions, ultimately achieve more from their classroom experience, and will be more productive members of group projects.

Technology cannot be separated from the life of the community in the world of education. Each part has its own function and advantages. The hardware and software used to create and run multimedia applications is known as multimedia technology (Kapi et al., 2017). Multimedia technology has several characteristics such as integration, diversity, and interaction that support people to communicate information or ideas digitally. Multimedia is a combination of more than one type of media such as text (alphabetical or numeric), symbols, images, images, audio, video, and animation usually with the help of technology for the purpose of improving understanding or memorization (Guan et al., 2018). It supports verbal instruction with the use of static and dynamic images in the form of visualization technology for better expression and

understanding (Alemdag and Cagiltay, 2018; Chen and Liu, 2008).

Basically, multimedia technologies for educational purposes can be categorized according to whether they are used for teaching or learning. Several different multimedia or digital learning resources are listed in Ready and Lockyer (2013). Furthermore, according to Guan et al. (2018), several studies have established the importance of multi-media technology for education and the widespread adoption of multi-media devices. Multimedia generally uses technology and the application of multimedia widely in education because of its many benefits (Almara'beh et al., 2015). Multimedia application tools have benefits for teaching and learning which are summarized as follows:

- 1) Ability to turn abstract concepts into concrete content
- 2) The ability to present large amounts of information in a limited time with little effort
- 3) Ability to trigger students' interest in learning
- 4) Provide the ability for teachers to know the position of students in the learning.

Technology is used to present many things in collaboration with

multimedia, one of which is PowerPoint. It is a presentation program developed by Microsoft that creates a slide show of important information, charts, and images for a presentation. It is most often used for business and school presentations. The use of technology in developing communication skills is often used and collaborated with the multimedia contained in the PowerPoint. Anggraini (2010) conducted research related to the application of technology in the classroom. The study revealed that students who applied PowerPoint presentations improved their speaking skills. PowerPoint presentations are computer software that facilitates learners to learn creatively and interactively. The research findings show that before implementing the English program and applying PowerPoint presentations as a teaching and learning technique, there were 25 out of 37 participants (68%) who performed 'enough' presentation skills, while 12 participants (32%) were categorized as 'poor'. After being given a model of effective presentation skills, the results show that there is a lot of improvement in doing this method. pernah sampai kepada pembaca yang ingin dituju. Jadi,

sebaiknya judul dibuat agar lebih spesifik.

Teaching and learning method hold the big effect to motivation and confidence in communication skill. The term learning is often indicated as an educational effort that is carried out intentionally and structured, added with goals that are set before the process is carried out, with controlled implementation. Learning activities can be emphasized that in the educational process often a person learns accidentally, without knowing the purpose in advance, and is not always controlled in terms of content, time, process, and results, but the two terms – education and learning are used interchangeably (Yusuf Hadi Miarso 2009:4). In learning, the indicator of learning concentration is important to obtain strategies for conveying the material. The characteristics of learning concentration are:

1) Engkoswara (2012) in an article written by Aprilia, et al (2014), with seven indicators of learning concentration as follows:

- a. The readiness of knowledge that can appear immediately when needed.
- b. Able to apply the acquired knowledge.

- c. Able to analyse the acquired knowledge.
- d. There is acceptance or attention to the subject matter.
- e. Responding to the material being taught.
- f. Able to express ideas/opinions.
- g. There is proper body movement according to the teacher's instructions.

2) Slameto (2010) in Nuramaliana (2016:25), with five indicators that affect learning concentration as follows:

- a. Lack of interest in the subjects being studied.
- b. Disturbed environmental conditions.
- c. Students' minds are confused.
- d. Student's health condition.
- e. Tired of the learning process that is going through.

With the World Inc. is an educational organization based in Japan that prioritizes the development of English communication for students.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is looking for an innovative way of upgrading communication skills using multimedia in presentations held by With The World Inc Japan. The research method used by the researcher gave significant results in student output. Data source was taken from 36 students of English Club SMK TI Bali

This is an Online International Student Education and Cultural Exchange Program based in Japan. With The World Inc. Programs connect students from all over the world in particular across Asian countries, and offer cross-cultural interaction experiences. Having the opportunity to engage in small group discussions with students in different countries, they can deepen their understanding of social issues and face multiple perspectives. Each program has a teacher assistant who will assist with communication. With The World Inc. program. attract students' attention to practice their communication and self-confidence and face to face with students from other countries. The topics discussed are also about the environment, daily life, culture, technology, and the SDGs.

Global Denpasar. Methods of data collection by direct observation and interviews. Nasution (2003: 56) says that "Observation is the basis of all science. Scientists can only work based on data, namely facts about reality obtained through observation. The researcher enters and sits in that class. Researchers must be in the classroom during the learning process,

sitting in their class, listening to the class, observing student movements, seeing and hearing for themselves the complaints of students about the learning process they get. Record what they see and hear, record what they say, think and feel.

At the data collection stage, observations can be categorized into direct observation, participatory observation, and indirect observation, according to Danial (2009: 77-79) when viewed from his work, Direct Observations are observations made directly by observers on the objects observed in this study. The researcher observes directly how the classroom atmosphere, student character, learning materials, learning process, and student interaction. By doing direct observation the

author can obtain the necessary data in accordance with field conditions. The results of observations for qualitative data require categorization, a description of the observed phenomena, by arranging in detail, chronologically, and structurally, so that the data becomes a unified whole as it is. Researchers directly follow the activities in the classroom, starting from the initial activities, core activities, and closing activities.

Data analysis techniques are carried out using data analysis techniques proposed by Miles and Huberman (Sugiyono, 2009: 91) which include data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions or verification.

Figure 1: Data Collection flow

Figure 2: Data Analysis flow

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

With The World Inc. Japan provides a new learning experience for students to improve their communication skills in English. This program uses Multimedia presentations with PowerPoint as a learning model. students to communicate in English is often triggered by meeting with students from other countries via online, understanding each other and exchanging discussion information given as a project. The following are examples of several tables presented from the results of this study.

Table 1. The result of Pre-Test questionnaires on student response to question one.

NO.	QUESTION	PERCENTAGE		
		Yes, I Do Like It	It's Just Fine	No, I Don't Like. It's Boring
1.	Do you enjoy the online class based on modul discussion	15.6% (9 students)	24.6% (15 students)	59.8% (37 students)

Based on table 1. In the first question, given 3 choices of questionnaire that have not been implemented on With the World Inc. Program. The result was that 37 students (59.8%) answered “No, I don’t like”. The remaining 15 students (24.6%) answered “Its’s just fine” and

the last 9 students (15.6%) answered, “Yes, I do like it”.

Table 2. The result of Post-Test questionnaires on student response to question one.

NO	QUESTIO N	PERCENTAGE		
		Online Class (Based On Textbook)	Offline Class (Based On Textbook)	Online Class (WTW program)
1.	What learning Model do you prefer?	5.5% (4 students)	10.5% (6 students)	84% (51 students)

Based on table 1. In the first question, given 3 choices of questionnaire that have been implemented on With the World Inc. Program. The result was that 51 students (84%) preferred join With the World Inc. Program. The remaining 6 students (10.5%) choose to join Offline Class (based on textbook) and the last 4 students (15.6%) choose to join Online Class (based on textbook)

Table 3. The result of Post-Test questionnaires on student response to question one.

No.	Question	PRECENTAGE	
		Yes, I like it so much	No, I don't like it
2.	Do you like/enjoy WTW Program	93.4% (57 students)	6.6% (6 students)

Based on Table 3, in the first question, given 2 choices of questionnaire that

have been implemented on With the World Inc. Program. The result was that 57 students (93.4%) answered “Like” the Online Class based on textbook. The remaining 6 students (6.6%) answered “No, I don’t. It’s boring” with the Online Class based on Modul.

THE POSITIVE IMPACTS

Based on the data shown from the results of the research above, it can be concluded that With the World Inc. Program has a lot of positive impacts on students. Some of the findings that can be found are as follows:

1. Encourage students’ self-confidence

The data shows that confidence in communicating is the most difficult thing for students to do in conveying their ideas or ideas. The WTW program provides an extraordinary experience because the presentation topics are very familiar to students. When self-confidence increases, the desire to learn will come without coercion from outsiders. Based on the results of the post-test and questionnaire, the comments below can be seen.

“I am very happy to be able to participate in the WTW program, at first I was hesitant to join it, but when I tried it, I felt more confident when presenting

in front of Japanese, Indies, and Taiwanese students, because we both studied English. So, I’m not afraid to be wrong to speak. I used to feel inferior and O...M...G... it’s so fun meeting Beautiful Girl from Japan LOL. I hope the WTW program continues at my school”

“About WTW I really really appreciate and love with the idea (Making this program). I think that everybody at least need to meet new people across the country! It is either to make new friends or enhance your bravery by speaking with them (Or enhance your English speaking); I hereby thank you for making this a thing! I would definitely join again anytime!”

2. Enjoying and Fun Learning

Based on the data above, WTW Program can be used as the assessment Tool received a positive response from students because they find it interesting. After participating in With the World Inc. Program once, many students are interested in joining the next program again. Fun learning will only succeed if the students themselves state that it is fun.

“A really enjoying program, really fun and i like it soo much”

“I think the WTW program is the best program I've ever participated in, because from there I can make a lot of new friends”

“An amazing experience IMO, everything was great”

“The program is really good, should do it more because its entertaining and helping us to study English more”

3. Improving Speaking Ability

All participants agreed that With the World Inc. Program was able to improve and develop their speaking skills, as stated in the following statements.

“For me this program is a very very good program, because I can interact with foreign students and hone my communication skills, especially in English”

“I think the WTW program is the best program I've ever participated in, because from there I can make a lot of new friends and improve my speaking skill a lot better now”

Questioner shows the number of positive and interested student comments with the With The World Inc program. Japan to continue to run.

Figure3: Questioner result from students

Student's Expression Show The Motivation And Joy

The seven learning motivation indicators indicators according to Engkoswara (2012) in an article written by Aprilia, et al (2014), and Slameto (2010) in Nuramaliana (2016: 25), namely:

- a. There is acceptance or attention to the subject matter. The students accept the project given by making PowerPoint presentation with animated multimedia
- b. Responding to the material being taught. The students respond by doing communication, games, quiz via online meeting.
- c. There is proper body movement according to the teacher's instructions. The body language by laughing, smiling, waving hand, and stay tune on camera show their motivation in learning.

- d. Able to apply the acquired knowledge. They used to talking in English after the program with their English Club team.
- e. Able to express ideas/opinions. They do the good communication with students from Japan, India, Vietnam and Taiwan by answering each question related to the topic.
- f. Interested in the subjects studied. Questioner shows their comment to apply again to this program.
- g. Not bored with the learning process that is passed. Students shared their experience in writing their story related to the program that has been passed.

Figure2: WTW Program AJ21 with Kansai Soka High School Japan and AJ22 with ODM Public School India

CONCLUSION

By this research all teachers are expected to be able to design learning media as innovations by utilizing the technology. Teachers conduct online learning simultaneously by groups on social media such as WhatsApp, telegram, Instagram, zoom applications or other learning media. In this way, teachers can ensure that students take part in learning at the same time, even at different places. This research gain the great result based on the problem that arises. The interaction of students in joining With The World.Inc program by doing creative presentation of PowerPoint shows the great responds of their motivation to do communication in English. The confidence is increasing by this program. Effective communication skills are the basis for success in many aspects of life.

In future research, researchers want to continue the use of technology, video or quizziz in presenting the culture of their respective countries. Collaboration with other countries provides a new atmosphere and unique motivation for students to improve their communication skills in English. The use of technology and applications also

plays an important role in improving the quality of education.

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